

POSSIBILITIES OF PHILOSOPHICAL AND ARTISTIC INTERPRETATION IN
THE STORIES OF KHURSHID DOSTMUHAMMAD

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Annotation: *This article discusses the possibilities of philosophical and artistic interpretation in the works of Khurshid Dostmuhammad based on the story "Jajman".*

Keywords: *Jajman, bazaar, nojins creature, Zoroaster, symbolism.*

H. Dostmuhammad's story "Jajman" is guided by the principle of creating a national character by depicting artistic images in extraordinary situations. The writer also shows the protagonist's attitude to various unusual situations, thus encouraging the reader to draw universal, philosophical conclusions. In Jajman, the market is described as a symbol of life. The main plot of the story is the uproar of the nojin creature called Jajman among the people of the market. "H. Dostmuhammad copied the creature in 'Jajman' into a novel. So where did this creature, the infidel, come into the building? "Only Zoroaster can admit that he escaped from the prison of the human body," writes literary scholar D. Kuronov about the author's novel "Market".

In fact, the story of "Jajman" begins with an abstract depiction of a quiet market life:

"The power of evil has reached me!" Hmmm, let's just say I've seen better.

At the heart of this painful curse in the morning ... "Jajman is at the center of this and all that will happen next. This creature, sometimes openly or secretly, steals the things of the traders in the market. Someone loses a raisin, someone loses a pickle, someone loses money. The people of the bazaar only cry for a moment when there is a tragedy. According to the author's idea, in order to understand the negative events that take place in human life, one must first have a pure heart and faith.

"Grandpa could clearly see the face of this strange creature - the creature's eyes, ears, and beak shone incessantly like those of a mouse and a fox." he shook his head at once, thinking, "The fox seems to have come from a mouse," and after a moment's silence, he whispered, "The belly belongs to a kangaroo ..." ! " he thought, and hurriedly hugged her, as if in doubt. "

There is life in the observation of Doctor of Philology D.Kuronov. Indeed, Jajman is a symbol of NAFS who "escaped from prison in the body of the people". According to Eastern philosophy, there are two kinds of lust: satanic lust and human lust. When a person renounces faith and religion and follows in the footsteps of Satan, then a satanic lust arises. Then evil will come upon the earth. doomsday is approaching. If a person is able to control the satanic nafs with a rope of patience, if he overcomes the merciful nafs, the life of

mankind will be prosperous. His spirit rises. Focuses on the status of the perfect human being.

The great thinker Jalaliddin Rumi's "Inside is Inside" says: "Man is a talking animal." The original meaning is: "The nourishment of animalism in man is the things and desires that arouse lust, and the nourishment of humanity is the knowledge, wisdom and beauty of God. This is not Rumi's invention, but the essence of human life. This wisdom is called the struggle between good and evil in mythology, and dialectical law in Western philosophy. From a particle of good to the greatest of goodness, from a scorpion of evil to the lowest of evil, it is subject to this law.

The novelty of H. Dostmuhammad's work is that he painted a philosophical image of the national character through the symbol of Nafs, which was achieved by incorporating the ancient Eastern Zoroastrian philosophy into artistic reality.

There is no portrait of any character other than Jajman in the play. The author relates them all to the reader's imagination. Zoroaster draws the portrait of Jajman perfectly in the language of his grandfather.

Jajman embodies the quality of all living things on earth. That's why Zoroaster, when he first saw Grandpa Jajman, hesitated, not knowing what he looked like. We think that this is where the writer refers to the symbol. The fact that Jajman is like nothing at all at the same time is a sign that lust is characteristic of living beings. Because there is no creature without lust. At the same time, the need for lust is limitless. The more freedom he is given, the more he needs. The creature called Jajman has a similar feature.

According to ancient legends, when God created the nafs, He asked him, "Who am I?" Then the nafs replied, "You are this, I am this." Angered by this blasphemy, God burned him in hell for a thousand years and asked the same question. The answer is the same, no change. Another thousand years of torment in hell, and the answer to lust has not changed. For the last time, lust has been tormented for hundreds of thousands of years. Only then did he acknowledge God as his creator. Because of this, man will be subjected to the sufferings of this world and, in the end, to Hell only because of his own desires. Jajman also acts under the auspices of Ahriman, a symbol of evil. Only Zoroaster's grandfather knows this.

Symbolically, the market is the way of life of mankind, the wall of the story, the boundary between evil and good. This wall is constantly rattling. Ahriman, who lives behind him, tries to break down the wall and add the human world to his dark world. As the story unfolds, the rumble of the tim wall grows louder and louder. At the beginning of the story: ". " The rumors about Jajman will come true. People want to understand him, they want to caress him, they want to see him. Even one of the sorghum sellers;

"Let's agree with Manashi the mouse." He eats as much as he can, and he doesn't swallow the world like an angishwana does. they bury the blame; they say, "It was fun, Tim was homeless, we fed ourselves if you didn't cut the four nuts."

The image of Zoroaster's dream, which is given at this point in the story, also has a symbolic meaning. In his dream, Zoroaster takes his grandmother Otash (Fire is a symbol of resurrection in Zoroastrianism) in the palm of a giant blue eye. When he wakes up, he

sees that his grandmother is dead. From this dream comes the conclusion that forgetting the lessons of the ancestors, forgetting oneself, being a slave to lust. It is as if the holy grandfather Zoroaster, the holy fire, warns of calamities.

In the market, however, Jajman's second attack begins. Now all the people in the market are plotting to kill Jajman, led by Bobo, the son of a walnut seller. At the urging of Jiydafurush, Zoroaster came to receive a blessing from his grandfather. firstly, Ahriman's threat, and secondly, Jajman's tree, which was moving in the distance, left the crowd unhappy with this good prayer. The crowd again leaves his grandfather alone and goes his own way. The next hurricane will be repeated when marketers are worried about their trades. Again, no one but this grandfather hears this voice. The roar grew louder and louder: "(Bobo) was turning his back on Tim, but he heard a roaring noise again. He stood up as if he had fallen to the ground and listened with his whole body: gurs ... gurs ... gurs ... "The crowd is unaware of anything, happy that Jajman has been chased away, saying, 'Jajman will no longer show his blackness.' Grandfather Zoroaster's worries grew day by day: "Is Jajman alone or does he have many descendants? Or what will people do if Jajman invades everywhere?" can't finish game "

Grandfather Zoroaster was the first to understand the secret of Jajman's insatiable appetite. For the first time, Otash sees a horrible squirrel that has taken his grandmother away. Jajman picked up his bag and threw it in the palm of his hand.

As the crowd grew louder and louder, the riot intensified. He could not get rid of the trouble by treating the market against Jajman and covering the holes with wire. A great reward was prepared for the one who caught Jajman. At that moment, the voice of Zoroaster's grandfather began to sound louder and louder. This was a sign of the imminence of the catastrophe. Pistachio seller urges Zoroaster to his grandfather: "We will catch him anyway! Even if you do not help, we will dry the seed of this idiot" Grandfather Zoroaster only prays: "

The crowd catches Jajman. Chalajon makes the situation. The noise is getting louder. When Jajman is pronounced dead by the crowd, he accidentally says:

"Lo ... kila! ... Loki ... la!" Only then did the crowd feel the need for Zoroaster. But now it was too late. he becomes aware of what happened when he tried to warn him.

Jajman is a completely symbolic and philosophical work. Here Bazar is a symbol of worldly life, Jajman is a symbol of lust, Zoroaster is a symbol of faith, belief, crowd is a symbol of ignorance. If we pay attention to the story, the market people will not hear the warnings and cries of Zoroaster. Because they do not hear, they try to overcome the nafs (Jajman) with ignorance. But in Eastern philosophy, it is said that lust can be overcome only through enlightenment. Enlightenment comes from understanding the Creator, through faith. Grandfather Zoroaster did not respond to any appeals from the crowd, but only asked Ahuramazda for help. Ignorant people do not have faith. A person without faith and enlightenment cannot overcome his desires. There is a risk of an attack.

So, H. Dostmuhammad's story "Jajman" embodies a high level of Eastern philosophy. In this way, the writer shows the negative features of the nature of the nation. It warns

mankind of the calamities that can follow. Zoroastrianism, with its mythical characters (Ahuramazda, Ahriman), served as a symbolic, artistic detail for the writer.

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